

Collaborative assembly with holographic cues

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Abstract—The industrial collaborative scenario is experiencing several changes, due to the influence of the new working paradigms introduced by the fourth technological revolution. In the proposed application, a cobot and a human agent have to collaborate to assemble the components of a thermostatic valve. The cobot is endowed with a cognitive unit, Smart Robots, equipped with artificial intelligence algorithms that enable it to recognize the latent co-worker intention and promote a proactive cooperation with the human partner, as well as adapting to his/her observed behaviour. Moreover, to facilitate the mutual understanding of the two agents and the fluency of the cooperation, the application exploits the recent advances in terms of mixed-reality technologies, Microsoft HoloLens, to create a visual holographic communication channel with the co-worker. This mixed-reality wearable head-set is used to display in the operator field of view intuitive and easy-to-understand information in the form of holographic task-related projections through which he/she can be guided, assisted and warn during the various phases of the overall collaboration. Consistently with the paradigm of Industry 4.0, whose cornerstones are the flexibility and the strong interconnection among the industrial devices, the collaborative station has been endowed with ultra-fast 5G connectivity, so as to guarantee a highly reliable and very low latency data exchange between the devices. This collaborative task has proved its efficiency in terms of robustness to error propagation and cycle-time.

Index Terms—human-robot interaction, mixed-reality, cognitive system, AI, holographic instructions, 5G

I. INTRODUCTION

The birth of the technological revolution known as 'Industry 4.0' has paved the way to new perspectives for what concerns collaborative robotics. In this scenario, the research is focusing on the problem of endowing the collaborative robot, also known as cobot, with a cognitive system that can enable it with the capability of recognizing in advance the underlying intention of its human partner, namely, what he/she is doing or he/she intends to do. Indeed, this aspect has proved to be beneficial according to several aspects of the cooperative team working, since it improves the effectiveness and fluency of the cooperation, as long as the two agents, human and robot, can share a mutual understanding of each other, [1], [2].

Given the above, cobots are becoming full-fledged rational agents in the sense that they are increasingly equipped with sophisticated artificial intelligence algorithms which allow them to cooperate with their human partner in a proactive way. However, the robot must not only be able to estimate

what its co-worker is actually doing, but also to create a clear communication channel through which it can potentially assist, when appropriate, the partner during the execution of the current task. The need for the operator to be supported during the execution of a certain task seems to be also motivated by the novel working industrial framework that the fourth technological revolution is introducing. In fact, in this context, the overall flexibility of the manufacturing lines, as well as the interconnection of a number of machines and systems, are of paramount importance. This new scenario entails a clear change in the operator working conditions and role. Indeed, he/she will be less and less required to perform the same repetitive task for the overall working day; conversely, he/she will be increasingly assigned to different activities, for instance, distinct assembly operations during the same working day. Given the above, the robot can exploit mixed-reality devices as an alternative communication channel through which it can convey to the human operator explicit cues concerning the progress of the current operation or task-related information that can provide assistance to him/her during the execution of the current task, [3], [4], [5].

II. COLLABORATIVE ASSEMBLY TASK

The proposed approach is evaluated in a real industrial application which consists in a collaborative assembly task. A schematic representation is illustrated in Fig. 1. More specifically, in the presented scenario, the human and the robot are required to cooperate in a synergic way to assemble the components of the head of a thermostatic valve. During this collaboration, the human operator is monitored by a device that constitutes the actual cognitive system of the entire application. This unit, produced by Smart Robots, a spin-off of Politecnico di Milano, is a 3D vision sensor that has been equipped with sophisticated artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms. Through the integration with these AI algorithms, the robot is endowed, to some extent, with artificial intelligence capabilities that allow it not only to perceive the human but also to recognize and predict his/her activity. Due to the presence of this cognitive system, the robot can then choose which action it can perform during the various phases of the cooperation, based on the activity executed by its human co-worker. Thanks to these AI algorithms, developed by Politecnico di Milano, the cobot's activities

Fig. 1. Layout of the collaborative assembly station: Smart Robots monitors the human and recognizes his/her action that is then communicated to the robot; the human operator, wearing the HoloLens, is also supported during the cooperation by means of task-related holographic cues

are not static with respect to the specific collaborative task, conversely, the cobot adapts itself to the activity chosen by its partner by modifying its cycle online. Once Smart Robots has recognized the partner's intention in terms of operator's hand reaching target, the human agent is assisted and guided through a wearable mixed-reality device, Microsoft HoloLens. This device promptly shows, in the form of holographic projection, 3D animations or textual instructions related to the operation the human has to perform with the chosen component or the next part (as well as its position) he/she has to take to finalize the current activity. Moreover, potential holographic error messages warn the operator in the case he/she is trying to execute an inadmissible action. All this holographic content is task-related and displayed by the device in the appropriate location of the user's real working station. In addition, the holographic application shows the agent an interface through which he/she can receive a feedback about what he/she is currently doing, according to what has been perceived by Smart Robots, thus improving his/her awareness. The collaborative working station has also been equipped with ultra-fast 5G connectivity, provided by the Vodafone cellular network, so that all the devices involved in the cooperation could communicate among each other extremely fast, with very low latency time. Indeed, this aspect is perfectly consistent with the paradigm itself of the fourth industrial revolution, whose cornerstone is represented by the highly flexibility of the interconnected systems.

III. SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

Based on the observation of the worker's upper body motions, the proposed system can recognize immediately, or even predict, a potential erroneous action executed by the operator during the various phases of the assembly task. This feature makes the system robust with respect to the problem of error propagation over the cycle time.

The transformation of the working station, from a manual to a collaborative one, has produced several advantages, namely, the reduction of cycle-time and a greater robustness with respect to the fluctuations of the takt-time. Evidence of this are reported in a study presented to the conference INCOM 2018 (IFAC Symposium on Information Control Problems in Manufacturing), [6], where the application of the algorithms mentioned previously resulted in a reduction of the cycle time from 10% to 17%. In addition, the new collaborative station has preserved the same foot-print (2 sqm), if compared to the completely automated solution. The setup time of the collaborative station, as well as the layout reconfiguration, have been reduced to only few minutes, due to the possibility of recognizing quickly the human hand reaching areas (goal locations) by means of QR codes positioned in the corresponding regions. Eventually the use of a mixed-reality device has the benefit of discouraging the sense of alienation perceived by the operator during the execution of repetitive tasks. Moreover, it allows to instruct the potential unexperienced worker in a quick, intuitive and autonomous way, without requiring additional dedicated human resources. The choice of the HoloLens seems to be the most appealing solution for this context, since this head-set can be simply worn by the operator and can display, easy-to-understand and directly readable information in the form of holographic cues. Thanks to this solution, the time required to the operator to learn a new task is decreased.

For what concerns the performance of the wireless communication in terms of speed, the diagnostic tests have proved a highly reliable (up to 10 Gbps) and low latency (less than 4s) communication capabilities.

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